

Random Matrices, Gaussian Distributions and Level Crossing Avoidance

Francesco R. Ruggeri Hanwell, N.B. And SPN Messina Oct. 31, 2023

Random matrix theory often treats matrix elements x as being distributed according to a Gaussian distribution, $\exp(-.5xx)$. If the matrix is the Hamiltonian, this implies the Gaussian distribution applies to energy eigenvalues (in the diagonal form), i.e. one has an $\exp(-a e_i e_i)$ form. It is noted in (1) that such an approach leads to a kind of energy level crossing avoidance, i.e. $P(s) = .5s \exp(-ss/e)$ where s is the spacing between energy levels so $P(s) = 0$.

In this note, we try to investigate whether the level crossing avoidance is a direct consequence of the Gaussian approach used to establish the random matrix procedure. In particular, we ask why one would not assume energy levels with a constant probability in some energy range. Such an approach is often used in statistics, for example may be applied to power law energy distribution. There is no energy being distributed for energy eigenvalues, but the energy eigenvalues which follow from the Schrodinger equation (or a relativistic equation) automatically ensure orthogonal energy eigenfunctions. This implies that energy levels do not lie arbitrarily close to each other, nor do the eigenfunctions. We argue that this property of energy eigenvalues seems to rule out a constant probability for energy levels. One is then forced to choose some other physical approach, perhaps one which maximizes entropy so to speak subject to a constraint. One cannot use average energy as the constraint as there is no distribution of energy as in a gas. One may, however, apply a constraint to the energy squared, i.e. the second moment, and find that a Gaussian in variable energy is the solution. In such a case, energy eigenvalues distributed according to a Gaussian should automatically lead to level crossing avoidance, as one has rejected a constant distribution in energy in place of a Gaussian, we argue.

Schrodinger Equation for Bound States

The Schrodinger equation may be used to solve for bound energy eigenvalues and eigenfunctions in the nonrelativistic case. (The Klein-Gordon, Dirac or some other equation may be used in the relativistic case.) Mathematically, the energy levels are associated with orthogonal eigenfunctions and tend not to be equally spaced (except in the oscillator case). In other words, in order for eigenfunctions to be orthogonal, they cannot be arbitrarily close to each other in form and we suggest that the same holds for the eigenvalues. These considerations have no bearing if one may solve for energy eigenvalues and eigenfunctions exactly. If, however, one suggests replacing the exact solutions of energy eigenvalues of the Schrodinger equation with a random matrix, i.e. a Hamiltonian with random matrix elements (energy eigenvalues in the diagonal case), there should still be a link to basic physics associated with the exact eigenvalues and eigenfunctions. In particular, we argue that even though statistical approaches seem to lose information, one cannot lose the information that different energy levels should be associated with orthogonal eigenfunctions and so neither the eigenvalues or eigenfunctions may be arbitrarily close to each other, we argue.

Maxwell-Boltzmann Gas

We consider briefly the case of a microcanonical gas of n particles moving in one dimension. The total energy is constrained:

$$\sum_{i=1, n} e_i = E \quad ((1))$$

If particle n has energy e , then an energy $E-e$ remains. In the case of three particles, if the third has energy e , the second may have any energy within 0 to $E-e$ with equal probability as the third particle picks up the remaining energy. This type of argument leads to a probability distribution:

$P(e)$ proportional to $(E-e)^{n-2}$ ((2))

In the high n limit, ((2)) approaches an exponential form $\exp(-e/T)$.

One may see that the above argument is based directly on distributing a total energy E among n particles. In other words, there is a constraint on the total energy. One may relax this constraint when creating a canonical distribution and apply:

$$\sum_{i=1}^n e_i P(e_i) = E \quad ((3))$$

The point we wish to make is that any distribution has an Eave value. The constraint in ((3)) really means that one physically distributes energy in a gas (through two body collisions etc). Thus, statistical considerations like ((3)) are ultimately associated with physical constraints. We suggest that a similar line of reasoning should be applied to random Hamiltonian matrix elements.

Random Hamiltonian Matrix

One may solve the nonrelativistic Schrodinger equation (or a relativistic equation) to find orthogonal eigenfunctions and their associated energy eigenvalues. The orthogonality is not only a mathematical property, but a physical one because a real wavefunction squared represents spatial density. Thus, actual solutions of the Schrodinger equation try to keep eigenfunctions different (i.e. orthogonal) to each other and this, in general, leads to energy eigenvalues which have a certain spacing, i.e. do not become arbitrarily close to each other. In the case of the quantum oscillator, the spacing is constant.

As a result, we argue that if one tries to replace quantum energy eigenvalues with a statistical distribution, this distribution must respect the basic physics associated with the energy eigenvalues. In the above section of the microcanonical gas, we considered three particles and a total energy of E . If particle 1 has energy e , then particle 2 may have any energy from 0 to $E-e$ with equal probability, as there is no physical constraint preventing the third particle from picking up the remaining energy. In the case of energy eigenvalue, however, there is a physical constraint. Different eigenfunctions cannot become arbitrarily close and still remain orthogonal and this we argue has consequences for eigenvalues. We thus suggest that one cannot assume that energy eigenvalues are distributed with equal probability within an certain energy range. As a result, one must choose some other statistical scheme. This alternative scheme then should automatically lead to a result for which $P(s)$ tends to 0 for s tending to 0, where s is the separation of energy eigenvalues.

In the case of a gas, we argued that there exists a constraint on total energy, but no such constraint exists for energy levels of a Hamiltonian. Thus, one cannot have equal probability energy levels and one does not have a constraint on total energy which may be combined with a maximization of energy type approach. We thus suggest that one use the second moment, i.e. (Energy energy) average. This should automatically ensure that one does not have level crossing as one has rejected the equal energy level probability from the outset. We thus argue that it comes as no surprise that the random matrix approach, using Gaussian distributions of the matrix elements of the Hamiltonian leads to the avoidance of level crossings as noted in (1).

Avoidance of Energy Level Crossing with Random Matrix Theory

We consider now the usual random matrix theory which leads to an avoidance of the crossing of energy levels. (1) begins with a 2×2 matrix with elements x_1, x_2 on the first row and x_3, x_4 on the second. The eigenvalues are.

$$x_1 + x_2 \pm \sqrt{(x_1 - x_2)^2 + 4x_3x_4} \quad ((4))$$

The spacing of the two (i.e. difference) is: $s = \sqrt{(x_1 - x_2)(x_1 - x_2) + 4x_3x_3}$ ((5))

(1) uses a Gaussian distribution a priori for x_1, x_2, x_3 and writes:

$$P(s) = \int dx_1 dx_2 dx_3 C \exp(-.5x_1x_1) \exp(-.5x_2x_2) \exp(-.5x_3x_3) \delta(s - \sqrt{(x_1 - x_2)(x_1 - x_2) + 4x_3x_3}) \quad ((6))$$

(1) computes ((6)) directly by changing variables and ultimately obtains:

$$P(s) \text{ proportional to } s \exp(-ss/4) \quad ((7))$$

(1) argues that for s approaching 0, the probability approaches 0, i.e. spacing does not tend to 0 or energy levels avoid coming to close. We have argued above that this is a result which is guaranteed by the choice of the distribution, i.e. namely the Gaussian applied to the second moment of the variable x , i.e. $\exp(-.5xx)$.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that random matrix theory, which applies a priori a Gaussian distribution to matrix elements in the form of $\exp(-.5xx)$, often points out $P(s) = \text{probability for a spacing } s \text{ of eigenvalues} = .5 s \exp(-ss/4)$ leads to $P(s=0) = 0$. In other words, it is argued in (1) that random matrix theory tends to lead to an avoidance of energy level crossing, i.e. eigenvalues (energy eigenvalues in the case of the H matrix) do not come arbitrarily close to each other.

We argue that this result seems to follow from the use of the Gaussian distribution in the first place. We suggest that the exact solution of energy eigenvalues and eigenfunctions (Schrodinger equation solutions) leads to orthogonal eigenfunctions. This is a math result with physical implications as the eigenfunction squared (real function) represents spatial density. As a result, physically energy eigenfunctions cannot be arbitrarily close to each other and neither can their corresponding energy eigenvalues. This property cannot be ignored when one moves away from exact energy eigenvalue solutions and considers a statistical approach, we argue. As a result, one cannot have energy eigenvalues equally distributed in a certain energy range. Rejecting such a distribution means one rejects arbitrarily close energy level spacing. One may thus consider a kind of maximization of entropy approach subject to a constraint, but there is no constraint on energy as in a microcanonical ensemble. It thus seems that one considers the second moment, i.e. energy squared., or a Gaussian in energy energy. We argue then that it is no surprise that such an approach does not allow for energy levels to become arbitrarily close i.e. for $P(s=\text{spacing}=0)=0$ as follows from $P(s) = .5s \exp(-ss/4)$.

References

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